

Using Primavera Software in Construction Scheduling, Access at Primavera

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Annotation. Timely consideration of factors related to the effectiveness of construction and installation works in the construction industry is a key point in operational and production planning and management.

Key words: construction and installation work, scheduling, working methods.

Teamwork in projects is regulated in Primavera by the access function, which determines the level of user access, the functionality of the system, and the specifics of these projects. Access is distributed by the OSCE. This allows the user to have different access rights to different projects or parts of them.

Figure 1 Primavera Permission System

The project describes the process of achieving the results of the project. Each task in the schedule is at a certain WBS level and is characterized by completion dates and percentages, a calendar, and a type of relationship with other tasks. It is also possible to link the work of different projects. All this allows you to simulate almost any situation in the calendar network table. The work can be divided into stages of elementary actions with priority and percentage of completion. They provide an additional opportunity to standardize performance appraisal procedures. In man- and machine-hours, labor productivity can be measured in units of materials used, in different percentages of productivity, in physical volumes.

Figure 2 To Do List and Schedule

Resources: people, machines and mechanisms, materials

Primavera allows you to plan the use of company resources in several projects at the same time due to a single hierarchical structure of resources (resource reserve). Resources are divided into three main types: labor (people), machines (machines and mechanisms, equipment) and materials. Each resource can work according to its own calendar, use several prices, and also have different specializations. Any number of resource tables can be started. Their specialization and skills are described using a role structure. Defining roles for work planning simplifies the planning process at an early stage. Plugins are used to tie delivery to runtime.

Figure 3 Resources: people, machines and mechanisms, materials motion graph

Budget and expenses

Costs and budgets can also represent the financial component of projects in Primavera. Primavera budget to check the project's financial constraints. EPS/WBS is distributed by structural levels. Project costs may consist of the cost of resources and fixed costs (expenses) attributed to the execution of work. All project costs are accounted for according to the composition of cost items. Primavera's functions can be extended with additional software modules that solve the problems of forming capital investment plans, financing plans, maintaining contracts and acts of work performed, budgeting, and integrating with accounting systems.

Figure 4 Budget and Cost Graph

Results of work and documents

The project will be accompanied by a number of documents reflecting its technical, financial and other aspects. Project documentation may refer to preliminary activities or resulting events or components of the project. Primavera allows you to track copyright, manage versions, revision history, current status, and many other document settings. Primavera provides control over project workflow features, including document storage, cataloging, and approval processes.

Figure 5 Work results and documentation

References

- 1.Атаев,С.С.Технология строительного производства: Учебник для вузов/ С.С.Атаев, Н.Н. Данилов, Б.В. Прыкин и др.-М.:Стройиздат, 2010.-559с ,ил.
- 2.Баркалов,С.А.Управление персоналом, владеющим смежными профессиями /С.А.Баркалов,А.Е.Бережецкая,И.В.Федорова/ /Вестник ВГА-СУ, 2009, Том 5, №3.-с.161-163.
- 3.Голуб Л.Г. АСУ строительного треста / Л.Г.Голуб, Е.Н.Ляшенко. -М.:Стройиздат, 1976.-111с.
- 4.Панченко Н.М. Свойства и особенности строительных технологических процессов / Н.М. Панченко // Вестник гражданских инженеров.-2007/№3(12).-с.45-48
- 5.Джабриев А.Н., Досымбетов Н.Б «Отличие простых приемов от планирования системы ЭГЕМ в производстве строительного-монтажных работ» Международная научно-практическая, посвященная 100-летию со дня рождения профессора Виктора Алексеевича Афанасьева, СП-2023 стр.143-148